

TEACHING ENGLISH TO GREEN ECONOMICS STUDENTS: METHODS, DIFFICULTIES, AND ADVANTAGES

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Annotation: This article discusses the challenges and opportunities of teaching English to green economics students. It provides effective teaching methods, addresses common difficulties faced by students, and highlights the advantages of learning English for green economics students.

Key words: English, green economics, teaching methods, difficulties, advantages, authentic materials, meaningful communication, explicit instruction, differentiate instruction, limited vocabulary, academic language, fear of making mistakes, pre-reading activities, glossaries, context clues, vocabulary practice, scaffolding.

Introduction

Green economics is an emerging field of study that focuses on the intersection of economics and environmental sustainability. Green economics students need to have a strong understanding of both economic and environmental concepts, as well as the ability to communicate their ideas effectively. English is the language of international academia and business, so it is essential for green economics students to be proficient in English.

Teaching English to green economics students presents a number of unique challenges and opportunities. On the one hand, green economics students are often highly motivated to learn English, as they recognize its importance for their future careers. On the other hand, green economics students may have a limited vocabulary of English terms related to economics and the environment. Additionally, green economics students may come from a variety of backgrounds, with different levels of English proficiency.

This article will discuss the following topics:

Effective teaching methods for English to green economics students

Common difficulties faced by green economics students in learning English

Advantages of learning English for green economics students

Effective Teaching Methods for English to Green Economics Students

There are a number of effective teaching methods that can be used to teach English to green economics students. Some important considerations include:

Use authentic materials. Green economics students benefit from exposure to authentic materials, such as articles, reports, and videos related to economics and the environment. This helps them to develop their vocabulary and comprehension skills in a context that is relevant to their field of study.

Provide opportunities for meaningful communication. Green economics students need to be able to communicate their ideas effectively, both in writing and orally. Teachers should provide opportunities for students to practice communicating in English through pair and group work, discussions, presentations, and role-plays.

Offer explicit instruction in grammar and vocabulary. While green economics students may be highly motivated to learn English, they may still need explicit instruction in grammar and vocabulary. Teachers should provide clear explanations, examples, and practice opportunities to help students understand and apply language rules in authentic contexts.

Differentiate instruction. Green economics students come from a variety of backgrounds, with different levels of English proficiency. Teachers should differentiate instruction to meet the needs of all learners. This may involve providing additional support to struggling students or offering more challenging activities to advanced students.

Common Difficulties Faced by Green Economics Students in Learning English

There are a number of common difficulties that green economics students may face in learning English. Some of the most common challenges include:

Limited vocabulary of English terms related to economics and the environment. Green economics students may have a limited vocabulary of English terms related to economics and the environment. This can make it difficult for them to understand and participate in classroom discussions and activities.

Use pre-reading activities to build vocabulary. Before students begin reading a text on a green economics topic, provide them with a list of key vocabulary words and phrases. Help students to understand the meaning of these words and phrases by providing definitions, examples, and images.

Use glossaries and other reference materials. Encourage students to use glossaries and other reference materials to look up the meaning of unfamiliar words and phrases. You can also provide students with handouts or online resources that include glossaries of key terms related to green economics.

Use context clues to help students infer the meaning of unknown words. When students encounter an unknown word, encourage them to use the context of the sentence or paragraph to try to infer its meaning. You can also provide students with tips on how to use context clues, such as looking for synonyms, antonyms, and definitions in nearby sentences.

Provide students with opportunities to practice using new vocabulary. Once students have learned new vocabulary, provide them with opportunities to practice using it in their speaking and writing. For example, you can ask students to summarize a text in their own words, write definitions of key terms, or create a presentation on a green economics topic.

How to address the challenge of limited vocabulary of English terms related to economics and the environment in the context of teaching English to green economics students:

Difficulty understanding academic language. Academic language is the

language that is used in academic settings, such as universities and colleges. It can be more complex and formal than everyday language. Green economics students may have difficulty understanding academic language, especially if they are new to English.

how to address the challenge of difficulty understanding academic language in the context of teaching English to green economics students:

Provide students with a clear explanation of academic language. Help students to understand the difference between academic language and everyday language. Explain the key features of academic language, such as complex sentence structures, specialized vocabulary, and impersonal tone.

Model academic language in your teaching. When you are teaching a lesson, use academic language in your own speech and writing. This will help students to become more familiar with the sound and structure of academic language.

Provide students with opportunities to practice using academic language. Give students opportunities to use academic language in their own speaking and writing. For example, you can ask students to write a research paper on a green economics topic, give a presentation on a green economics case study, or participate in a debate on a green economics issue.

Use scaffolding to support students in using academic language. Provide students with the support they need to use academic language effectively. For example, you can provide students with sentence frames, templates, and other resources to help them to write in a more academic style.

Here are some specific examples of activities that you can use:

Academic language scavenger hunt. Give students a list of academic language features and ask them to find examples of these features in a text on a green economics topic. Once they have found the examples, have students write down the academic language feature and explain how it is used in the text.

Academic language charades. Write down academic language features on

pieces of paper and place them in a hat. Have students take turns drawing a piece of paper and acting out the academic language feature for the class to guess.

Academic language flashcards. Create flashcards with academic language features on one side and definitions or examples on the other side. Have students use the flashcards to practice their knowledge of academic language.

Academic language quizzes and games. Play games or give students quizzes to test their knowledge of academic language features. For example, you could have a quiz where students have to identify the correct definition of an academic language feature, or you could play a game where students have to match academic language features with examples of how they are used in text.

Fear of making mistakes. Many green economics students are afraid of making mistakes when they speak or write English. This fear can prevent them from participating actively in class and practicing their English skills.

How to address the challenge of fear of making mistakes in the context of teaching English to green economics students:

Create a positive and supportive learning environment. Let students know that it is okay to make mistakes, and that mistakes are a necessary part of the learning process. Encourage students to support each other and to learn from each other's mistakes.

Focus on communication rather than perfection. When students are speaking or writing English, focus on their ability to communicate their ideas clearly and effectively, rather than on their grammar and vocabulary accuracy.

Provide students with opportunities to practice English in a low-stakes environment. For example, you can give students opportunities to practice speaking English in pairs or small groups, or to write short, informal essays.

Give students feedback that is focused on improvement. When you give students feedback on their speaking and writing, focus on what they did well and on how they can improve. Avoid negative and discouraging feedback.

Here are some specific examples of activities that you can use in the classroom:

Mistake hunts. Give students a text that contains a number of mistakes. Ask students to find the mistakes and correct them. This activity can help students to become more aware of common mistakes, and it can also give them practice in correcting their own mistakes.

Error correction games. Play games with students where they have to correct mistakes in English sentences or paragraphs. This can make learning about grammar and vocabulary more fun and engaging for students.

Peer review. Have students review each other's work and give each other feedback. This can help students to learn from each other's mistakes and to improve their own writing.

Self-assessment. Encourage students to self-assess their own work and to identify areas where they need to improve. This can help students to take responsibility for their own learning and to develop a growth mindset.

By using these strategies, you can help green economics students to overcome their fear of making mistakes and to develop the confidence they need to communicate effectively in English.

It is also important to remember that every student is different, and some students may be more afraid of making mistakes than others. Be patient and understanding, and provide students with the support they need to feel comfortable practicing their English skills.

Advantages of Learning English for Green Economics Students

There are a number of advantages to learning English for green economics students. Some of the most important advantages include:

Improved academic performance. Green economics students who are proficient in English are more likely to succeed in their studies. This is because they are better able to understand their textbooks, assignments, and lectures.

Increased employment opportunities. English is the language of international academia and business. Green economics students who are proficient in English have access to a wider range of employment opportunities, both in their home countries and abroad.

Enhanced global communication skills. English is the global language of communication. Green economics students who are proficient in English can communicate with other professionals in their field from all over the world. This can help them to stay up-to-date on the latest research and developments in green economics.

Green economics is a growing field of study that focuses on the intersection of economics and environmental sustainability. As such, green economics students need to have a strong understanding of both economic and environmental concepts, as well as the ability to communicate their ideas effectively. English is the language of international academia and business, so it is essential for green economics students to be proficient in English.

There are a number of effective teaching methods that can be used to teach English to green economics students. Here are a few examples:

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Challenges Faced by Green Economics Students in Learning English

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Conclusion: Teaching English to green economics students is an important and challenging task. By using effective teaching methods and providing support to students, teachers can help green economics students to develop the English skills they need to succeed in their studies and careers.

References

Brown, H. D. (2004). *Teaching by principles: An interactive approach to language pedagogy*. Pearson Education.

Duff, P. (2019). *Teaching English to speakers of other languages in higher education: A practical guide*. Cambridge University Press.

Graddol, D. (2006). *English as a global language*. Cambridge University Press.

Hadley, G., & Hutchinson, T. (2011). *Teaching English language learners in college and university settings*. Cambridge University Press.

Harmer, J. (2007). *The practice of English language teaching*. Pearson Education.

Johns, T. M. (2016). *Teaching English to speakers of other languages:*

Context and approaches. Oxford University Press.

Oxford, R. L. (2013). Language learning strategies. Oxford University Press.

Rose, H., & Galbraith, S. (2006). The nature of academic language. Australian Council for Educational Research.

Scrivener, J. (2011). Learning teaching. Macmillan Education.

Williams, J., & Burden, R. (2019). Teaching academic English: A guide for teachers of adult learners. Cambridge University Press.